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A CASE SERIES ON AMLODIPINE INDUCED EDEMA

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ABSTRACT

Hypertension is one of the most common clinical conditions encountered by the physicians. There are wide ranges of medications available for treatment of hypertension, in which Calcium Channel Blockers (CCBs) are one of the most commonly prescribing drugs. CCBs are potential antihypertensive agents but the main drawback of this group of drugs is it produces pedal edema which decreases the compliance. The main cause for CCB-induced edema is increased capillary hydrostatic pressure by arteriolar dilation. Amlodipine is a third generation calcium channel blocker used in adults and children above 6 years old for the treatment of hypertension, angina and other coronary artery disease. The drug exhibits constant pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics and well tolerated but has more incidence of pedal edema than the other calcium channel blockers often leading to noncompliance and discontinuation of drug. This review article is aiming to explain the calcium channel blocker in particular amlodipine - associated edema and resolution of edema through the use of other hypertensive agents. Here we present 5 cases of different age group patients diagnosed with hypertension, type II diabetes mellitus, hemorrhagic stroke, CVA and gastritis who gradually developed pitting type pedal edema after the initiation of oral Amlodipine of dose 5 mg. The symptoms improved on cessation of amlodipine and the patient was managed with an alternative antihypertensive agents. Here, we set up the relationship between the suspected drug and the adverse reaction observed by performing causality assessment. The early detection, discontinuation of offending drug and prescription of alternative hypertensive agent improves patient's condition and restores normal quality of life.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hypertension is generally referred as a elevated levels of pressure of blood on the walls of arteries^[1]. Causes generally includes a pre existing diabetes, stress, familial history, excess salt intake, smoking and alcohol, narrowing of kidney artery, endocrine disorder and birth control pills^[2,3]. The presence of this disease shows some symptoms like lightheadedness, anxiety, vertigo, tinnitus, altered vision and often leads to fainting episodes^[4]. Treatment includes the non pharmacological therapy like reduced salt intake, anger management, and performing exercises. Beta blockers are the main line drugs when treatment is done pharmacologically. As beta blockers generally treat anxiety conditions, they are not suitable for longer durations of treatment^[13]. This makes the calcium channel blockers as a main stay treatment for longer durations.

Calcium channel blockers are more potent than beta blockers at decreasing cardio vascular mortality^[7]. CCBs reduce excitability of heart muscles, so these are used to treat abnormal heart rhythms^[6]. These are generally used to reduce blood pressure, cerebral vasospasm, reduce chest pain caused by angina. These can influence aldosterone synthesis in adreno cortical cells^[6]. The first generation CCBs are generally effective, but their rapid onset of action and shorter duration of action made them as second line drug, making third generation CCBs effective for reduction of blood pressure for longer days^[14].

Amlodipine is a third generation CCB. It is generally used to treat elevated blood pressure, CAD, angina^[5]. It generally acts by 2 ways: firstly, it inhibits movement of calcium ions into vascular smooth muscle and cardiac smooth muscle, causing vasodilatation, leads to increased peripheral vascular resistance and reduces blood pressure. Second, it reduces total peripheral resistance which reduces rate pressure product, and reduces oxygen demand in angina^[9]. Amlodipine causes edema, dizziness, palpitations and flushing^[10]. The occurrence of edema is found to be high at a rate of 10.8% followed by palpitations, dizziness, fatigue, flushing^[11]. We in our hospital setting found the edema with higher rate of occurrence and the primary mechanism involved was increased peripheral vascular resistance^[9]. The other uncommon effects include fatigue, abdominal pain, somnolence^[5], impotence, peripheral neuropathy, insomnia, tachycardia, gingival enlargement and jaundice^[5,12]. The rate of occurrence of edema is three times more in women than in men^[11]. The occurrence can be prevented by ACEs or ARBs^[9]. Amlodipine worsens protienuria in nephropathy patients^[8].

Case 1:

A 59 years male patient was admitted in general medicine with the chief complaints of blood pressure, associated with breathlessness. He was a known smoker and alcoholic since 23 years, known case of Hypertension since 5 years, on irregular treatment and Type-II Diabetes Mellitus since 9 years and on treatment with metformin 500mg.

General Physical examination of the patient was conscious and responding to oral commands. His vitals were: B.P- 172/104 mm of Hg, Pulse-89 bpm, CNS- Semi-conscious, P/A-Soft, non-tender, CVS-S1S2 + and his laboratory investigations were found to be Hb- 11gm%, The diabetic profile shows Random Blood Sugar-279 mgs/dl, HbA1C-7.5%, Renal and Liver function tests are within normal limits. Electrocardiograph shows no changes. So, based on subjective and objective evaluation patient was diagnosed as Hypertension with Type-II Diabetes Mellitus.

On day-1 the patient was treated with following medication: T. metformin of 500mg twice daily, T. amlodipine of 5mg once daily, iv fluids and B.complex once daily along with T. metaprolol of 50mg once daily. No fresh complaints on day-2 and chest pain have reduced, so patient was continued with the same medications. On the 4th day after initiation of amlodipine therapy, patient developed Bilateral Pedal pitting edema, as shown in the. This edema was mainly due to the T. Amlodipine. The common ADR's of Amlodipine is headache and ankle edema. On day-7 we intimated the condition of the patient to the doctor about the drug and doctor dechallenged . to check whether the reaction was due to amlodipine, the patient was re-challenged. Patient shown similar complaints after 24 hrs of therapy. So, he was treated with T. lasix of 20mg once daily to reduce edema.

Case2:

A 55-year-old female experienced angioedema during hospitalization for a right thalamic hemorrhagic stroke. She had no past history of angioedema and all of her medications were assessed for risk of angioedema. After careful evaluation, case reports linking calcium channel blockers and angioedema led to further examination of amlodipine as a cause. Amlodipine therapy had been initiated 24 hours prior to the development of angioedema, which then resolved 72 hours after discontinuation of the drug. Patient was undergone rechallenge with amlodipine and she had similar complaints after 24 hrs of the re administration. So, the ADR was likely to be caused by amlodipine.

Case 3:

A 72 year old female patient was admitted to surgery ward with complaints of heart burn aggravated by food, abdominal pain. On further interviewing, she was a known case of diabetes mellitus, under oral hypoglycemic agent (glimeperide 2mg+metformin 500mg) for past 3 years. Before 3 months the patient was also diagnosed with hypertension and was under irregular medication.

By examining the vital sign, blood pressure was found to be 140/90 mmHg, pulse rate 74 beats per minute and all other laboratory investigations such as complete blood count, liver function test urine analysis, chest X ray, electrocardiograph seems to be normal. The diabetic profile shows Random blood glucose- 252mg/dl, HbA1C-7%. From the subjective, laboratory examination and past history of patient she was diagnosed with type II diabetes mellitus, hypertension and gastritis. The patient was treated with intravenous administration of Ranitidine 50mg twice daily, glimepride2mg+metformin 500mg, Amlodipine.5mg orally once daily . On the 4th day after initiation of amlodipine therapy, the patient was presented with pedal edema (pitting type). The physician interprets that the pedal edema was caused by amlodipine. On cessation of amlodipine the patient was recovered from edema.

Case 4:

A 42 years male patient was admitted in general medicine dept. with chief complaints of elevated blood pressure, weakness of both upper and lower limbs. He was a known alcoholic and smoker since 10years. He was a known case of hypertension since 5 years and CVA under treatment since 6 months. His BP: 180/100 mmhg, PR: 84 bpm, CNS: right hemi paralysis present, and his RBS: 74mg/dl, CT-Brain- multiple cell necrosis present. So, based on subjective and objective evaluation patient was diagnosed as a recurrent CVA. On day-1 the patient was treated with ecosprin 150mg od, clopidogrel-75mg od, atorvastatin 40 mg od, T.amlodipine of 5mg od, ceftriaxone 1gm iv bd, pantoprazole 40 mg iv bd, IV Fluids, and physiotherapy. No fresh complaints on day-2, so patient was continued with the same medications, this treatment was continued for 7 days. From 2nd day to 6th day patient was gradually developed pitting type of pedal edema. This edema was mainly due to the T. Amlodipine. The common ADR's of Amlodipine is headache and edema. On day-7 we intimated the condition of the patient to the doctor about the drug and doctor dechallenged the drug after that patient was recovered from the oedema. So, based on these results the patient had developed pedal oedema due to the T. Amlodipine.

Case 5:

A 81-year-old woman with essential hypertension who had not been treated with any other drug was prescribed amlodipine 5 mg/day to control her blood pressure along with propranolol of 40mg once daily. She was continued with same medications for 4 days. since from third day She developed anasarca edema soon after amlodipine administration. Her laboratory investigations revealed her HB: 10gm/dl, and all her LFT and RFT values were found normal. Discontinuation of amlodipine resulted in dramatic improvement. For providing an alert card, she had undergone Re-challenge with the same drug and similar complaints were observed. So, in this case the reaction is caused due to the administration of amlodipine. She was advised to stop amlodipine and continued with olmesartan of 40mg instead of that.

ASSESSMENT OF ADR:

To evaluate the relation of adr and the drug we had performed causality assessment, severity, predictability and preventability of ADR

Causality assessment:

WHO-UMC: certain (3 cases), probable (2 cases).

Naranjos assessment scale: probable (3 cases), possible (2 cases)

Kirsch and lasagnas scale: definite in all cases

Severity: level 4a in 3 and level 3 in 2 cases.

Predictability: it is a predictable reaction.

Preventability: definitely preventable.

All the observed ADRs were reported.

DISCUSSION

The potency of CCBs made them as one of the first line treatment of hypertension either in mono or in a combination therapy. Our cases are represented with edema because of amlodipine therapy. The mechanism considered to occur in pedal edema is due to increased hydrostatic pressure across capillaries which result in reflex constriction of post capillary vessels. The treatment includes alternative along with stopping or continuation of the drug in some cases. Frequent adverse effects reported with Amlodipine are nausea, abdominal pain, vomiting, dry mouth, constipation, gingival hypertrophy, dizziness, heartburn, photosensitivity, headache, light headedness and insomnia, hot flushes, palpitations, ECG abnormalities, chest pain, atrioventricular block, hypersensitivity reactions, frequent urination and elevated liver enzyme. The general step taken in patients with CCBs induced pedal edema includes the addition of a diuretic generally a thiazide or using an alternative with ARBs or ACEs. A combination of diuretic, CCB, and ARb is a common practice now a days. It also provides an information for physicians to have monitor while using CCBs alone.

CONCLUSION

The cause of oedema in these cases is due to Amlodipine, so physicians should have a close monitor of the patient's condition during the administration of drug like Amlodipine. Amlodipine induced pedal edema was reported at an incidence rate of 1.8- 10.8% on a dose between 2.5 to 10mg daily. The health care professionals should carefully monitor the patients while administering the CCBs majorly amlodipine. The early detection, discontinuation of offending drug and prescription of alternative hypertensive agent improves patient's condition and restores normal quality of life. Further investigations over the drug may be essential to change future prescribing pattern of the drug

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ABBREVIATIONS:

- CCB : calcium channel blocker
 CVA : cerebro vascular accident.
 HbA1c : glycated heamoglobin
 CAD : coronary artery disease.
 ACE : angiotensin converting enzyme
 ARB : angiotensin receptor blockers
 CNS : central nervous system
 CVS : cardio vascular system
 ADR : adverse drug reaction.
 CT : computed tomography.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All authors would like to declare that there are no competing interests to disclose.

REFERENCES

1. Naish, Jeannette; Court, Denise Syndercombe (2014). Medical sciences (2 ed.). p. 562.
2. "High Blood Pressure Fact Sheet". CDC. 19 February 2015. Archived from the original on 6 March 2016. Retrieved 6 March 2016. Archived from the original on 26 December 2016.
3. Poulter NR; prabhakaran D; Caulfield, M (22 August 2015). "Hypertension.". *Lancet*. 389 (9995): 801-12.
4. Fisher ND, Williams GH (2005). "Hypertensive vascular disease". In Kasper DL, Braunwald E, Fauci AS, et al. *Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine* (16th ed.). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill. pp. 1463–81.
5. "Amlodipine besylate tablet". DailyMed. US National Library of Medicine. Archived from the original on 29 October 2015. Retrieved 5 November 2015.
6. Felizola SJ, Maekawa T, Nakamura Y, Satoh F, Ono Y, Kikuchi K, Aritomi S, Ikeda K, Yoshimura M, Tojo K, Sasano H (2014). "Voltage-gated calcium channels in the human adrenal and primary aldosteronism.". *J Steroid Biochem Mol Biol*. **144** (part B): 410–6. PMID 25151951
7. Chen N, Zhou M, Yang M, Guo J, Zhu C, Yang J, Wang Y, Yang X, He L (2010). "Calcium channel blockers versus other classes of drugs for hypertension". *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. **8**: CD003654.
8. Remuzzi G, Scheppati A, Ruggenti P (2002). "Clinical Practice. Nephropathy in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes". *New England Journal of Medicine*. **346** (15): 1145–51.
9. Li, Y. Robert (2015). *Cardiovascular Diseases: From Molecular Pharmacology to Evidence-Based Therapeutics*. John Wiley & Sons. ISBN 9780470915370. Archived from the original on 8 September 2017.
10. Russell, R. P. (1988). "Side effects of calcium channel blockers" (PDF). *Hypertension*. **11** (3 Pt 2): II42. ISSN 0194-911X. PMID 3280492
11. "Norvasc Prescribing Information" (PDF). Archived (PDF) from the original on 16 February 2017. Retrieved 3 July 2017.
12. Ono, M. et. al (2010). "Prevalence of Amlodipine-induced Gingival Overgrowth". *Int J Oral-Med Sci*. **9** (2): 96–100. doi:10.5466/ijoms.9.96. Retrieved July 10, 2017.
13. Livestrong.com, What is the difference between beta blockers an calcium channel blockers, Aug 14, 2017. Available from: <https://www.livestrong.com/article/18413-beta-blockers-weight-gain-side/>.
14. Aouam K, Berdeaux A. Dihydropyridines from the first to the fourth generation: Better effects and safety; 2003, july-ug; 58(4): 333-9.

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